

Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with
Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive
Gender Equality Plans

D4.3 Guidelines and recommendations for implementing 4I-GEPs in sports education and organisation

University of Gothenburg

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

CEE	Central and Eastern Europe
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
GA	Grounding action
GE	Gender equality
GEP	Gender equality plan
GBV	Gender-based violence
HEI	Higher education institution
IO	Implementing organisation
LD	Learning diary
LGBTQI+	Lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, queer, intersex + other identities
ML	Mutual learning
MLW	Mutual learning workshop
M&M	Monitoring and mentoring meetings
PE	Physical education
RD	Roadmap
WP	Work package
4I-GEP	Innovative, Intersectional, Inclusive and Impactful Gender Equality Plans

The SUPPORTER project

SUPPORTER, “SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans”, is an EU-funded project running from April 2023 until September 2025. Launched on 19. April 2023, it aims to support eight sports higher education institutions from Central and Eastern Europe in developing their own intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful Gender Equality Plans which explicitly address gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

Through mutual learning and interactive exchanges, the project will seek to:

1. Identify and document systemic challenges faced by sports higher education institutions in advancing gender equality and eradicating gender-based violence.
2. Develop activities tailored to each partner institution.
3. Strengthen the sports institutions’ organisational capacity to address gender equality with an intersectional approach.
4. Foster an inclusive institutional culture by developing mutual-learning processes.
5. Strengthen networking and exchange among sports institutions and with communities of practice
6. Foster gender-related institutional, sustainable, transformative changes in the sports institutions with a specific attention on the challenge of gender-based violence -thus ultimately fostering the institutions and their Gender Equality Plans’ inclusiveness and the overall adherence to intersectionality.

While initially partnering with eight institutions, the SUPPORTER project aspires to target and reach the wider sports ecosystem and its various organisations in Central and Eastern Europe and beyond, and in the long run contribute to wide societal changes.

Project Partners

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	Univerzitet u Banjoj Luci (UNIBL), Bosnia & Herzegovina
	Univerza v Ljubljani (UL), Slovenia
	Univerzita Karlova (CU), Czechia
	Natsionalna Sportna Akademiya Vassil Levski (NSA), Bulgaria
	Lietuvos Sporto Universitetas (LSU), Lithuania
	Universitatea de Vest din Timisoara (UVT), Romania
	Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport (GSTUPES), Georgia
	Universitatea de Stat de Educație Fizică și Sport (USEFS), Moldova

Summary

This deliverable presents guidelines and recommendations for implementing intersectional, innovative, inclusive, and impactful Gender Equality Plans (4I-GEPs) in higher sports education institutions and sports organisations. The recommendations build on lessons learned from the SUPPORTER project, in which eight Central and Eastern European institutions developed and implemented 4I-GEPs.

Key findings highlight the importance of:

- Establishing a shared, intersectional understanding of gender equality and gender-based violence.
- Developing robust policies, monitoring systems, and data collection methods that move beyond binary approaches.
- Ensuring active leadership support and engagement from diverse stakeholders.
- Embedding inclusiveness, innovation, and impact at every stage of institutional transformation.

The guidelines follow the six steps in the design and implementation of GEPs and conclude with targeted recommendations for universities, faculties, teachers, sports organisations, and coaches. These recommendations aim to support sustainable institutional change and foster broader societal transformation within the sports ecosystem.

Adopting a 4I perspective is crucial for achieving structural and sustainable change in research and higher education. 4I-GEPs contribute to institutional transformation by embedding gender+ equality across all levels of activity. By focusing on the 4Is, higher education institutions can ensure that gender+ equality becomes an integral part of everyday academic practice.

1. Introduction

Sports universities and faculties occupy a unique position to advance gender equality within the higher education landscape and promote wellbeing across the sports ecosystem. Implementing intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful Gender Equality Plans (4I-GEPs) enables institutions not only to embed gender equality into their structures but also to inspire broader cultural change. These institutions shape the next generation of coaches, educators, and athletes while leading efforts to promote gender equality and safeguard wellbeing more broadly. By adopting 4I-GEPs, higher education institutions can influence the wider sport ecosystem by educating coaches, physical education (PE) teachers, and athletes about gender equality and gender-based violence. They can also serve as role models for other higher education institutions and sport organisations, demonstrating how 4I-GEPs can drive cultural and structural change. Embedding gender equality principles into core structures and daily practices fosters environments where all students and staff – regardless of gender – feel recognised, respected, and supported.

Nevertheless, challenges persist. Sport higher education is not immune to the gendered dynamics present in both the sporting world and in higher education generally. Sports education often mirrors societal inequalities, including gender stereotypes, heteronormativity, sexism (Phipps et al. 2018; Denison 2021), and gender-based violence (Lipinsky et al. 2022; Humbert & Strid 2024a). Binary frameworks dominate, marginalising non-binary and LGBTQI+ students and staff, and reinforcing hierarchies and inequalities common in higher education (Melton & Cunningham 2014; Welch et al. 2021). This is associated with heightened risk of gender-based violence against non-binary staff and students (Humbert et al. 2024). Teaching and training within sport education often perpetuate these binary norms, reflecting broader practices in organised sport. Dominant forms of masculinity can marginalise alternative expressions of masculinity and femininity (Coakley & Pike 2013), increasing vulnerability for female and LGBTQI+ students and athletes to inequality, interpersonal violence, and gender-based violence. (Johansson & Lundqvist 2017; Parent et al. 2015; Vertommen et al. 2016). Despite these challenges, sports institutions possess significant transformative potential. Grounded in values of integrity, respect, and fair play, they are well positioned to pioneer inclusive, equitable practices. By actively fostering a culture of integrity, fair-play, and respect - values traditionally promoted through sports (Opstoel et al. 2020) - institutions can promote equity and inclusion. Moreover, taking concrete steps to protect and safeguard athletes from emotional and psychological abuse (Safesport International 2014), strengthens efforts to prevent gender-based violence. Integrating these principles into daily teaching, research, and training allows sports higher education institutions and sports organisations to create environments where inclusion is not only encouraged but expected.

This deliverable builds on lessons learned through SUPPORTER activities, including training sessions, mutual learning workshops, monitoring and mentoring meetings, roadmaps, and learning diaries. It provides guidelines for designing and sustaining 4I-GEPs, as well recommendations tailored to diverse stakeholders in the sports ecosystem. The SUPPORTER Implementing Organisations (IOs) – eight higher education sport institutions in Central and Eastern Europe – have developed intersectional, innovative, inclusive and potentially impactful GEPs to achieve structural and sustainable change in research and higher education. These plans contribute to institutional transformation by embedding gender+ equality across all levels of activity. By focusing on the 4Is, higher education institutions can ensure that gender+ equality becomes an integrated part of everyday academic practice. The process of developing 4I-GEPs included training, mutual

learning (ML), monitoring and mentoring meetings (M&M), roadmap (RM) development, and the use of learning diaries (LD) throughout the development process.

1.1 Aim

The aim of this deliverable is to present the SUPPORTER guidelines and recommendations for implementing intersectional, innovative, inclusive, and impactful GEPs in the sport higher education field.

The deliverable is structured in three parts: **First**, it analyses the experiences related to efforts on gender mainstreaming in sports higher education. **Second**, it provides guidelines for integrating the gender dimension, including gender-based violence into sport institutions and ensuring their sustainability over time. **Third**, building on the guidelines, it formulates recommendations tailored to various target groups within the sports ecosystem.

1.2 The SUPPORTER sport higher education institutions

Eight sports HEIs started their journey toward developing intersectional, innovative, inclusive, and impactful GEPs in April 2023. Prior to the initiation of the project proposal, all but one had a valid university-wide GEP. In some cases, initial baseline GEPs meeting only the minimum requirements were co-developed during the proposal writing stage. None of the GEPs included a clear definition of gender equality, and only one was specific to the sports environment. While some forms of gender-based violence, such as sexual harassment, were addressed, acknowledgement of gender-based violence as an overarching form of violence was generally lacking. Most GEPs targeted students, academic staff, and non-academic staff, with a specific focus on women and men. Only three of the initial GEPs addressed multiple inequalities; however, none adopted an intersectional perspective, instead, treating inequalities in isolation.

While some of IOs had prior experience and existing policies in place, for most participants, the SUPPORTER project marked their first structured engagement with gender equality and gender-based violence measures. Learnings from the development and implementation of 4I-GEPs within these IOs apply to a variety of institutional contexts, including: a) country context, both within and outside of the EU context; b) socio-political contexts, reflecting different levels of support and interference; and c) previous experience with gender equality and gender-based violence initiatives.

Table 1: Description of IOs

IO	Type of organisation	No. students	Teaching & research	Initial GEP
UNIBL, Bosnia and Herzegovina	Public higher education and research institution. Faculty of Physical Education and Sport.	15 000	Teaching and research in the field of physical education and sport	University GEP (2022-2026)
UL, Slovenia	Public higher education and research institution. Faculty of sport.		Educational, professional and scientific research institution in the field of kinesiology and sport	University general policy on violence, harassment and bullying (2022-)
CU, Czechia	Public higher education and research institution. Faculty of Physical Education & Sport	100 000	Research and teaching in the field of professionals in sport, physical education,	University Equal Opportunities

			military physical education, civil protection education, sport management, recreation and physiotherapy.	Plan (2022-2024)
NSA, Bulgaria	Specialised higher education and research institution Sport university	10 000	Sports education and research	University GEP (2022 – 2025)
LSU, Lithuania	Specialised public higher education and research institution Sport university	1450	Research and teaching in sport science	University GEP (2024)
UVT, Romania	Public higher education and research institution. Faculty of Physical Education and Sports	15 000	Teaching in Physical Education and Sports. Research Center for Physical Education, Sport and Kinesitherapy.	University GEP (2022-2023)
GSTUPES, Georgia	State University of PE and Sport	750	Teaching in physical education and sport.	University GEP (no date)
USEFS, Moldova	State University of Physical Education and Sport	2200	Teaching in physical education and sport. Scientific Centre for research activities	University GEP 2021-2025

1.3 Key concepts

Gender+: Analysing gender requires recognising its constant interrelation with other grounds of inequality, including age, disability, ethnicity, race, and social class (Walby et al. 2012). Gender is therefore not understood in isolation but as intrinsically linked to intersecting axes of power.

Gender balance participation: Refers to the representation of women or men in any decision-making body in public and political life, with neither falling below the 40% parity threshold (EIGE Glossary). Within the European Research Area (ERA), gender balance in participation concerns both the researchers involved in project implementation and those in leadership and decision making (European Commission 2023).

Gender-based violence: Encompasses all forms of violence, violations, and abuse based on gender, extending beyond narrow legalistic definitions. Gender-based violence includes physical, psychological, economic/financial, and sexual violence, as well as sexual and gender harassment, stalking, organisational violence and harassment, and emerging forms of violence not yet formally recognised. It occurs in both online and offline contexts and manifests in physical, psychological, emotional, and interactive forms, as well as through informal and/or formal leadership dynamics. Gender-based violence is part of a wider system of dominance and power inequalities that transcends binary understandings of gender and may involve sexist and racist hostility or threats (Hearn et al. 2022; Strid et al. 2021).

Gender equality: Refers to equal visibility, empowerment, and participation of women and men across all spheres of public and private life. It entails valuing and accepting differences between women and men, as well as the diverse roles they play in society, on an equal basis. Achieving

gender equality also requires structural changes that challenge and transform the unequal power relations between women and men, aiming for a better balance in values and priorities associated with each (Council of Europe). Gender equality has been a priority of the ERA since the 2012 ERA Communication. The European Commission set three objectives to work with EU Member States and foster institutional change: (1) gender equality in research careers at all levels, (2) gender balance in decision-making, and (3) the integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation content (Council of the EU 2015).

Innovative: An innovative GEP introduces measures that demonstrate originality and creativity in fostering gender equality. This may involve new ideas, concepts, and approaches; advanced participatory methods; unconventional partnerships; or targeted actions addressing emerging challenges. In short, an innovative GEP provides out-of-the-box, inclusive, intersectional, and impactful solutions to common gender equality issues (SUPPORTER 2025).

Intersectional: An intersectional GEP situates gender in relation to other sociocultural, economic, and political inequalities such as race, ethnicity, class, sexuality, age, (dis)ability, and nationality. It proposes actions that acknowledge and address the ways in which different forms of inequality and disadvantage intersect (SUPPORTER 2025).

Inclusive: Inclusiveness in GEPs should be integrated into their design, implementation, and evaluation in four key ways: 1) Inequalities and inclusivity – considering gender in relation to other sociocultural factors such as race, ethnicity, age, sexuality, and disability, and actively and explicitly paying attention to the inclusion of marginalised groups. 2) Geographical inclusiveness recognising regional and local differences between organisations and enabling knowledge transfer from more advanced to less experienced institutions, and vice versa. 3) Internal inclusiveness – engaging stakeholders at all levels, including students, administrative and academic staff, and top management. 4) Intersectoral inclusiveness – involving external stakeholders beyond academia (SUPPORTER 2025).

Impactful: An impactful GEP strengthens an organisation's institutional capacity for gender mainstreaming across a series of intermediate stages and themes for change. Twelve key themes have been identified: (1) establishing a core team of change agents; (2) building their capacity and skills; (3) ensuring leadership commitment; (4) securing resources; (5) data collection and statistical analysis; (6) internal stakeholder involvement; (7) external stakeholder and expert engagement; (8) coverage across dimensions of gender equality; (9) institutional change; (10) transparency and accountability; (11) policy-making informed by robust understandings of gender equality; (12) organisational culture and governance (SUPPORTER 2025).

1.4 Material and methods

The material consists of training sessions (n=9), mutual learning workshops (n=8), IOs sets of learning diaries (n=55), and the analysis thereof as reported in SUPPORTER Deliverables D2.2 (Grahm et al. 2023), D4.1 (Ververidou et al. 2024), and D4.2 (Ververidou et al. 2025) and the analysis of the SUPPORTER resistance questionnaire (Vilarchao et al. 2025). To engage the IOs in the process of developing recommendations, one learning diary (LD5) was specifically dedicated to recommendations from the IOs. Additionally, to further enhance mutual learning regarding lessons learned and recommendations, discussions on the topic were integrated in the MLW in Ljubljana on 20 March 2025 to enable IOs to discuss and provide input to recommendations. Furthermore, during the process of collection and analysis, a series of reflective

meetings (n=3) were held in the core team (ESF, SEERC and UGOT) to discuss lessons learned from M&Ms, MLWs, training sessions, and the implementation of roadmaps.

The data analysis consisted of collecting lessons learned from efforts in gender mainstreaming and addressing gender-based violence and documenting them under three main themes: the political/policy context, formal institutions, and the informal institutional context. These themes were developed inductively, through a review and reflection on previous deliverables, as well as discussions of experiences from training sessions, mutual learning workshops, and monitoring and mentoring activities. They were further structured around different aspects that emerged from challenges encountered during the planning and implementation of the roadmaps. Each aspect was supported with evidence drawn from previous deliverables, learning diaries, and notes from reflective meetings and workshops. In the running texts, aspects are presented in italics. In addition, positive examples from the work of the IOs were collected during the analysis of the lessons learned.

Building on the identified lessons learned, guidelines based on the six steps of a GEP were developed. These guidelines were designed to address both the regulative organisational pillar – drawing on the analysis of political/policy context and formal institutions – and the cognitive-cultural pillar – drawing on the analysis of the informal institution context. In addition, the guidelines provide recommendations on how to sustain the activities implemented, informed by the analysis on sustainability.

Lastly, recommendations were developed to address how sport institutions can integrate the gender dimension, including gender-based violence, in their gender equality work and specifically in their new GEPs. The recommendations are presented by target group.

1.5 Structure of the report

The deliverable consists of four parts. First, the introduction outlines the aims of the deliverable followed by the background and methods used to analyse lessons learned and develop guidelines and recommendations. The second part presents the experiences reported, drawing on data collected throughout the project and the corresponding analysis, as summarised in SUPPORTER deliverables, MLW, ML meetings, and LDs submitted by IOs. This part concludes with a summary of lessons learned. The third part provides guidelines derived from the analysis of these lessons. Finally, the fourth part presents recommendations for diverse target groups within in the sports field.

2. Lessons learned regarding efforts on gender mainstreaming

The SUPPORTER Deliverable D2.1, *Inclusive Gender+ Equality and Policy and Practice* (Strid et al. 2024) identified seven recommended areas for integrating the gender dimension and addressing gender-based violence in sports higher education. These recommendations were based on the state-of-the-art, and identification of best policy and practices related to the implementation of 4I GEPs in sport higher education. In this deliverable (D4.3), we build on these recommendations to analyse lessons learned, i.e. experiences regarding efforts on gender mainstreaming in sports higher education institutions. The seven recommendations from D2.1 are: 1. Establish conceptual

clarity and shared understandings. 2. Shape policies effectively. 3. Work-life balance and organizational culture. 4. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making. 5. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression. 6. Integrate the gender dimension into research and teaching. 7. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

These recommendations are grounded in the EU's five fields of action for achieving gender equality in research and higher education: Work-life balance and organisational culture.

- Gender-balance in leadership and decision-making.
- Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.
- Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content.
- Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment.

In this deliverable we present these recommendations, followed by the related challenges reported by IOs and the strategies/actions they employed during the process of planning and implementing GEPs at their institutions. Finally, we discuss how resistances work as a challenge and obstacle for implementing the 4I-GEPs and how the IOs plan to work to sustain their actions on gender equality beyond the project's lifetime.

2.1 Shared understanding

SUPPORTER D2.1 (Strid et al. 2024) recommends developing clear concepts and a shared understanding of the issues to address. At the policy level, an initial challenge was the *lack of visibility and communication of the GEP*. At the start of the SUPPORTER project, all IOs had overarching GEPs covering the macro level, without being specifically tied to sports higher education. Moreover, the GEPs were not considered to be communicated internally or externally and were therefore often unknown to staff and students. To address this lack of visibility, four roadmaps included actions to enhance the visibility and communication of their GEPs.

Furthermore, it is important to recognise that *gender inequalities and stereotypes are embedded in the sports environment*. This is also reflected in IOs' descriptions of their institutions. The sports ecosystem is largely characterised as male-dominated, with a male-centric and highly competitive culture. IOs also identified a general *lack of awareness* regarding gender equality, Gender+, and gender-based violence within their institutions. During the SUPPORTER project, it became clear that IOs sometimes conflated gender balance with gender equality, making it difficult to recognise other forms of inequality (Gender+) beyond the numerical representation of women and men.

Additionally, a *binary approach to gender in IOs and lack of intersectionality* were found, which results in a tendency to equate gender with a focus on women. A shared understanding of the concept of intersectionality also proved to be a challenge. This may stem from the persistence of a binary approach in society, higher education, and sports. Sport, in particular, has been described as "operating in 'inequalities silos'" (Vilarchao et al. 2024, p. 2). As an example, one of the IOs expressed: "At [our department] and Faculty level we operationalise gender in binary terms due to the specific in the wider societal context" (UNIBL, LD1). Additionally, challenges related to polarised opinions, stereotypes, and prejudices were expressed. However, to challenge lack of intersectionality, a couple of IOs explicitly worked to include diversity in the core group as well as persons with knowledge on intersectionality.

Lastly, a challenge identified was that *awareness raising do not engage all stakeholders and lack sport specificity*. This challenge included a lack of engagement from both internal and external

stakeholders, as well as the absence of an established culture in which gender equality is seen as a natural or integral concern.

To address challenges related to lack of a shared understanding all roadmaps included a grounding action on awareness raising for both staff and students, focusing on clarifying gender+ equality and inequalities within education and the context of sports. While working with the roadmaps, several IOs found gender equality and gender-based violence to be delicate topics that not all staff and students felt comfortable discussing or addressing. Many of the IOs also reported experiencing low interest in participation from their institution. Some also perceived a lack of understanding among stakeholders regarding the significance and objectives of the initiative. Reluctance to change may be part of uncertainty and unconscious resistance.

One example on how IOs worked to address these challenges was to develop and establish regular communication with stakeholders and one IO explained that a lesson learned was to involve senior management as advocates for gender equality at the institution, to increase staff engagement. Low participation was also tackled through shortening and rescheduling workshops to avoid exam periods; using more interactive and engaging formats in the awareness-raising activities; combining with events that attract high participation (e.g. induction week in GSTUPES); and leveraging the influence of the student union in the student community.

Further, transitions need change agents; however, some IO representatives did not seem to consider themselves as change agents and seemed to lack motivation, sometimes – though not always - based on fear for one's career, to drive the process forward. The identified challenges imply a general lack of a shared understanding of the importance of change. To respond to the lack of ownership, trainings during the process of developing and implementing 4I-GEPs engaged with being a change agent within sport higher education. By the end of the project, several IO representatives identified themselves as change agents, demonstrating a shift in perspective and greater confidence in assuming this new responsibility within their institutions (UL, UNIBL).

Positive examples

Positive experiences from planning and organising the awareness raising campaign to reach internal and external stakeholders (LD, GSTUPES)

Combining awareness-raising initiatives with existing institutional, national and international events significantly increases visibility and maximises impact (LD6: UL, CU)

The invitation of gender experts and practitioners as speakers enriched discussions and gave away a sense of authority (LD6, UNIBL)

Mandatory training on social security on gender-based violence for faculty staff (LD, CU)

Using personal stories by inspiring speakers that serve as role models is an effective way to raise awareness (LD, CU, LSU**)

A good practice is to engage student representatives in the organisation of awareness raising activities on gender equality in sports environments, which has ensured more active student engagement (LD, UNIBL, UL, CU)

Prioritise diversity and intersectionality in the core group (LD, CU and UL)

Designing events around inclusion and emotional connection, using inclusive sports format and informal dialogue rather than only formal training, creates a highly positive atmosphere for open conversation (LD6, CU).

2.2 Policy

Based on the SUPPORTER D2.1 (Strid et al. 2024) it is recommended to have clear and verifiable objectives addressing multiple and intersectional forms of discrimination. In the beginning of the SUPPORTER project, there was a *lack of institutional policies facing gender equality and gender-based violence* as well as the inclusion of an intersectional approach. Even in cases where such GBV policies existed, awareness of staff and students was very low (CU, LSU). Also, policies did not sufficiently emphasise the intersection between the institutional, the sport higher education and widening dimensions. Further, having clear measures has initially been recognised as problematic at the involved institutions.

Analysis shows a *lack of both gender-related data and effective monitoring mechanisms*. Since a binary approach is dominating there was a lack of data beyond sex-disaggregated data. Some IOs also pointed to a lack of qualitative data. To address these issues IOs have been working on increasing data collection relevant for developing 4I-GEPs, by including a Grounding Action on data collection. As a result of intensive training and mutual learning activities on intersectionality (indicatively TM3, MLW in Thessaloniki) several IOs specifically added intersectional aspects (i.e. age, ethnic origin) in their data collection. One of the IOs (UNIBL) already collected the relevant qualitative and quantitative data as a pre-activity in creating their GEP, therefore they did not address this as a grounding action; they did, however, embed intersectionality throughout their new GEP, focusing on the combined impact of gender, age, position, and nationality. To address gender-based violence and sexual harassment, data collection on incidents was specifically included on this issue.

Another recommendation from the SUPPORTER D2.1 review (Strid et al. 2024) was to assure both infrastructures related to the policy and to grant budget and personnel. This was initially a problem among the IOs who experienced a *lack of allocation of adequate financial and human resources*. Several IOs had no equality officers and personnel lacked time to work with gender equality. During the project this was addressed by each IO dedicating resources for advancement on gender equality, either by establishing such bodies or expanding the responsibilities of existing ones (such as Ethics Committees and HR bodies). Where resources for external recruitment of GE experts could not be secured, internal appointment and relevant training were preferred. Even so, representatives from several IOs still felt that there was a lack of time and resources to work with gender equality during the project. For instance, some IOs introduced amendments in their roadmaps to address the lack of funding for their grounding actions.

Positive examples

Starting from already existing requirements and involving people to give a lot of ideas on how to complete the policy (LD, LSU)

A lesson learned is the importance to tailor the GEP to the institutional level, specific for challenges in sport education and to use the 4Is (presentation at MLW, CU)

Any new policy of the institution must be supported by a general context of information, adoption, monitoring and evaluation (LD, NSA)

One key lesson was the importance of clearly defining roles and procedures from the outset to avoid confusion and ensure trust in the system. (LD6, CU)

2.3 Work life balance and organisational culture

Previous research point to the importance of higher education acknowledging the risk of shaping hierarchical structures and uneven power relations and instead suggest taking the lead in changing norms and structures. To do so it is important to support employees as change agents (Strid et al. 2024). The IOs identified challenges directly related to work life balance: In mutual learning discussions, several of the IOS mentioned the complete detachment of women on parental leave from university advancements as well as the consequences of parental leave on career progression. However, work life balance did not occur as a single theme in the road maps of the IOs, except for one, in which the return from career breaks is an issue. However, *work life balance* can be seen as *interconnected to other identified gaps*, such as *lack of awareness* and *gender stereotypes embedded in the sports environment*. IOs acknowledge that the sport context is largely male dominated and consists of a male-centric and competitive culture. This does not only refer to athletes; the IOs underlined the challenges faced by female coaches in an equally male-dominated profession, from juggling between childcare and endless travelling to combatting stereotypes of male coaches being better – and thus preferred, even by female athletes. As such, these challenges are addressed by awareness raising campaigns on Gender+ and some IOs included Grounding Actions to work against gender stereotypes within sporting higher education context. Further, a few IOs included Grounding Actions on promoting gender-inclusive language in different institutional policies, recruitment calls etc. These actions can have a positive effect on work life balance. Connections can also be seen between work-life balance and organisational culture, recruitment and career progression.

A problem related to work life balance and organisational culture may be that institutions do not recognise this as an equality issue that needs to be handled. As such, it is important to highlight that a downside to not directly pinpointing this issue is that IOs may end up missing to include work-life balance in policies and infrastructure. To include means also to discover unknown in-equalities. Work life balance is an issue that is suggested to be important when working with equality, according to previous research and best practises (Strid et al. 2024). Even though work life balance was not acknowledged as a challenge while working on the grounding actions, this was still an issue raised in discussions during MLW. Positive examples raised during the workshops are presented below.

Positive examples

To support work life balance pioneering guidelines "*for provision of support during and after the career break*" were developed together with the university to reassure support to employees during and after career break (LD & GA, UNIBL)

A good practice is to include the employee union representatives in drafting the Guidelines to support career breaks (LD, UNIBL)

Early and inclusive engagement [to the development of the guidelines] led to strong institutional support from the beginning. By involving staff, students and management from the start, the development of the policies was smooth, with minimal resistance and constructive feedback throughout (LD6: UL, CU)

Suggestions to allow women on parental leave to participate in some academic meetings, committees etc. To enable inclusion and enabling a smoother transition between break and getting back to work (MLW, discussions during word café)

Suggestions to offer day care services at campus for employees and students who are parents. A similar suggestion was formed particularly for female coaches (MLW Strasbourg, discussions during word café and online MLW in September 2024)

2.4 Gender-balance in leadership and decision-making

Recommendations from SUPPORTER D2.1 (Strid et al. 2024) suggest that it is important to ensure the support of gender equality from the institution leaders and that they take gender into consideration when making decisions. A difficulty related to this recommendation, was that IOs identified *a reluctance to change at the institutional level* (see further, *resistance*). One such example was experiencing a lack of effort and coordination at the management level because of attitudes among persons in leading/management positions. Other challenges identified include that frequently, women staff are found to oversee day-to-day operations or appointed to nominally leading positions, while men hold the actual decision-making power. Along similar lines, it has been noted that women are sometimes reluctant to apply for such positions, which bear time-consuming responsibilities without additional remuneration.

A challenge related to gender-balance in leadership and decision-making was *lack of gender-disaggregated data* at the institution. Therefore, five IOs included Grounded Actions on data collection, directly or indirectly related to leadership, within their roadmaps. Further, all IOs, with available gender-disaggregated data during the co-creation process, identified an *uneven gender representation in leading and decision-making positions*. This unevenness was often beyond numerical inequalities. For instance, one IO explained that their academic board was man-dominated, while administration leadership was women-dominated.

Another recommendation from SUPPORTER D2.1 was to encourage employees to aspire to leadership positions. One challenge raised during the project was for women to aspire for such positions as increased responsibilities compounded by their care roles. This suggests a need for revising working conditions and/or rules for participation in leadership positions so that it is also possible for women to take one these roles.

A final recommendation based on research is for IOs to explore the opportunities to develop as a leader or coach. Suggestions are therefore to secure education for coaches and to work with networks and mentoring programmes (Strid et al. 2024). These aspects have been covered in the mutual learning workshops and training actions have been part of several roadmaps (e.g. LSU, UL).

Positive examples

It is especially good to have someone from management on the core team for implementing the project activities, as this ensures support throughout the whole process. (LD, UNIBL & UL)

The Committee of Academic Ethics was enlarged to 5 members to include two women (while previously only three men) to have a better gender balance (LD, NSA)

2.5 Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

Recommendations based on previous research suggest that it is important to secure routines for recruitments, including selection procedures at all levels to identify and act against biases (Strid et al. 2024). Even so, the IOs expressed that the challenges were less prominent in this theme due to laws and regulations directing the process of recruitment and promotion of personnel. This may be the case; however, a problem may be that IOs are thinking that laws and regulation is all that it takes to assure equality in the recruitment process and therefore are reluctant to see that recruitment and career progression may interact with several inequality aspects, that will affect the hiring process and career opportunities. For instance, understanding selection criteria based on described competence and professional merit only may lead to inequalities in the recruitment process. One IO gave a direct example of how lack of gender sensitive language in advertisements used for recruitment can hinder inclusivity and therefore may lead to persons not applying for the position.

Further, recommendations that are based on previous research suggest that “sports education/institutions should take a double approach and act on both a structural level to review routines and monitor processes, and on an individual level to support coaches and teacher”. (Strid et al. 2024, p. 43). This may be done by supporting coaches with networks and mentoring programmes and by securing equality for teachers/coaches in vulnerable positions due to for example gender, age, or hiring contract. Except for one IO, no specific grounded actions were suggested for gender equality in recruitment and career progression. However, just as with work-life balance and organisational culture, this is an area that can benefit from measures such as raising awareness of gender issues and challenging stereotypes. A suggestion discussed during the SUPPORTER project is the importance of securing equal recruitment by *tailored approaches in IOs in relation to recruitment and career progression*. One such tailored approach included in the grounding action of one IO was to use gender-sensitive language in recruitment calls.

Positive examples

Including working with gender sensitive language as a grounding action (GA 5, UL) can positively affect recruitment and career progression.

2.6 Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content

To assure that the gender dimension is included in teaching content and curricula (Strid et al. 2024) research recommends that courses include knowledge on equality and social justice and to help

students problematise structural perspectives of inequalities. It is also important to make sure that students know their rights as well as “how to support and act as part of a non-discrimination culture and environment” (Strid et al. 2024, p. 44). In the start of the SUPPORTER project IOs express that the *gender dimensions in research and education are not sufficiently covered* and that this content did not address sports. A challenge to integrate the gender dimension in teaching is described by the IOs as limited time and resources to do so. Also, the varying levels of awareness among teaching staff affect the extent to which gender is integrated into teaching content.

Several IOs included grounded actions on integrating the gender dimension in teaching. Some examples include the development of gender-relevant content in sports curricula, training on gender dimension in teaching and research, and the development of purposeful teaching methods. Incremental changes proved particularly effective. For integrating the gender dimension in research, IOs recognise a lack of research within the department/institution on gender as well as gender-based violence within sports environments. Several grounding actions addressed these challenges by encouraging researchers to explore gender related topics, and trainings on how to integrate gender in research.

Positive examples

Encourage students to include the topics of gender in student dissertations. Academic staff was encouraged to suggest such topic (example from MLW, LD-LSU)

Example on new teaching content: e.g., gender sensitive topic, history of equality in the country and gender equality in the future (example from MLW, UVT and UNIBL)

Meeting with other departments to prepare and discuss the inclusion of GE elements into curricula (LD, GSTUPES)

A suggestion is to use relevant cases stemming from life situations (sports and general). For example: students were encouraged to discuss the newly proposed law on banning LGBT propaganda in schools (LD, NSA)

Innovative research on uni-sex sports and unified sports with persons with disability (example from training and MLW, CU; LD-NSA)

Development of gender research and research cooperation between IOs (example from MLW)

2.7 Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment

To effectively integrate work against gender-based violence, IOs are recommended to have a holistic approach. The challenges identified by the IOs in the beginning of the SUPPORTER project, was that *gender-based violence including sexual harassment is unaddressed at institutional level*. On political/ policy level several countries lack precise legislation to address specific forms of gender-based violence. Further, within institutions policies and procedures preventing and addressing gender-based violence are absent. Importantly, and a key finding for many of the IOs: In cases where internal regulations do exist, there is still a lack of awareness of these; students and staff are unaware of existing gender-based violence policies, reporting and supporting

mechanisms at institutional level. To address these challenges all IOs included awareness raising on gender-based violence and sexual harassment in the context of sports.

Another challenge that IOs recognise is lack of reporting and support systems or systems in need of upgrading (see Humbert & Strid 2024b). Also lack of competence within the institution or faculty to prevent and work against gender-based violence are identified. This may lead to institutions/faculties observing however not acting on gender-based violence. Therefore, several IOs included trainings on gender-based violence for both internal and external stakeholders. These trainings were either standalone or embedded into curricula and professional training, such as Physical Education teacher workshops, Social Security course for academic and non-academic staff and training for coaches. Further, four IOs included establishing or revising internal procedures to address cases of gender-based violence. Examples are help/support systems, appointment of trust persons and adoption of protocols for preventing and dealing with gender-based violence within sport higher education.

Positive examples

Coach training session in which participants presented a lot of cases on gender inequality, harassment. Coaches shared experiences on how they dealt with cases related to discrimination based on gender, sexual orientation, disability or nationality (LD, LSU)

Getting approval from upper management for redefining the mandate for contact persons (ombuds persons) at the faculty (LD, e.g. CU, UL, UNIBL)

Training of students to know what to do if something happens

We initially planned to provide only written guidelines for the Confidential Help System, but feedback showed that staff and students preferred direct contact and verbal explanations. As a result, we organized short info sessions, which significantly improved understanding and trust in the system. (LD6, UL)

2.8 Resistances

Resistances against institutional change and gender equality measures in higher education are well documented in previous research (Strid et al. 2024). In SUPPORTER, such resistance has been identified at both institutional and individual levels and include e.g. cultural and normative resistance, leadership and faculty resistance, resource-based resistance, systemic resistance, and cognitive and psychological resistance – each with its specific concrete actions (Vilarchao et al. 2025). Within the frame of SUPPORTER, resistance has been experienced and explored during trainings, workshops and meeting, and explicitly via a questionnaire to the IOs.

A first observation from contrasting these materials is that the IOs identify fewer forms and lower levels of resistance than the core partners, who identify both a wider range and higher levels. Interestingly, what we can learn from this is that there is resistance to explicitly recognise or articulate the existence of resistance and its actual/empirical prevalence, hence: there is resistance to acknowledging resistance itself. Importantly, what we can hypothesise from the existence of this meta-level resistance is that there is a lack of understanding of the institutional change process, with resistance being viewed as a negative concept rather than a natural response to change. From

this, we can conclude that **it is of utmost importance for IOs to gain a deeper understanding of the institutional change process before initiating one.** This includes understanding what resistance entails, the various forms it can take (i.e. typology), and engaging in self-reflection to pre-identify potential types and subtypes of resistance that may be encountered during the months ahead in the organisations.

2.9 Sustainability

Making sure that actions are sustainable also after a gender equality project ends are of importance, and one of the three pillars, besides the organisational and cognitive cultural pillar. The SUPPORTER project seeks to foster and advance gender-related institutional, sustainable, transformative changes in higher education related to sports institutions. A further aim is to support networking and exchanges among sport institutions and communities of practice (internal and external stakeholders). Sustainability in this project approaches questions of long-term changes and continuities, changes that last, and benefit the policies and practices set around multiple gender, equality, intersectionality, inclusion and gender-based violence in higher education in sport institutions and beyond. A challenge recognised by the IOs was *keeping stake holders involved over time*. This proved to be difficult due to change of people during the project time and/or to lack of willingness from individual to invest time in the project as well as for staff willing to assist. This highlights the need for working to ensure continuous involvement and support from all stakeholders and to tailor engagement and strategies for keeping specific groups involved.

By fostering a more inclusive sports culture (in HEI, internal and external stakeholders, from grassroots to academia) this can drive societal and transformational changes based on principles of fair play and equality. These principles can take on a new enhanced meaning of ‘gender equality and intersectionality’ and strengthen societal cohesion and inclusion (Vilarchao et al. 2024).

The work with roadmaps underscores the importance of first establishing a robust foundation to be able to develop inclusive, innovative, intersectional, and impactful GEPs. Development of 4I GEPs need to consider organisation’s starting point, and the context that organisations stand within but also the formulation of long-term goals and their consequences. Based on the conclusions of (Ververidou et al. 2024) we suggest that sustainable change requires a stable base for promoting gender equality which considers the full complexity of intersecting identities and power dynamics. Thoughts on sustainability were specifically discussed during the Mutual Learning Workshop in December 2024. One recurrent point was that building structures that can stay (e.g. confidential support system) could bring long-term institutional change, along with creating permanent positions for trained personnel; embedding gender equality in existing tools (e.g. LSU’s annual psychological well-being survey).

Positive examples

Training on gender-based violence was included in a programme for social security piloted at the university. Based on the success of the piloted training the course will become mandatory for all staff at the faculty 2025 (LD, CU).

Planning to sign contracts of collaboration with external stakeholders (sport federations) for continuing to work to promote gender equality in the sports field (discussion in MLW, SUPES)

Some IOs have joined community of practises to sustain their work on gender equality (discussion, MLW)

Long-term strategic topics on GE should not just be adopted by the governing bodies but also be embedded in strategic documents but must also find a place so as to ensure continuity in the policies implemented (LD, NSA)

2.10 Summary of lessons learned

Lessons learned from the SUPPORTER project can be grouped into three main themes 1) the political/policy context; 2) formal institutions and 3) informal institutions. The themes reflect different aspects of challenges at various levels during the project, and how IOs have worked to address them. Based on the thematisation, efforts related to gender mainstreaming and addressing gender-based violence need to be tailored in such a way that they address norms and values (informal institutions), institutional structures and practices (formal institutions), rules and policies (political/policy context). An important lesson learned by the IOs was a broader understanding of the 4I framework and how to apply it in the development and implementation of GEPs. Summarising lessons learned according to the 4Is reveals both challenges and strengths. As mentioned, working with **intersectionality** proved to be a challenge, and the need to mould this concept into a *shared understanding* during the SUPPORTER project was found to be essential. Trainings and mutual learning proved to be valuable ways forward. A success of the project was that several IOs developed measures related to intersectionality.

Addressing intersectionality was also closely linked to **inclusiveness** – for example, some IOs worked specifically to ensure diversity within their core teams. Once again, establishing common ground required defining Gender+ and subsequently incorporating aspects such as age, socioeconomic background, and ethnicity into both measures and goals. Even so, the challenges faced by IOs in incorporating intersectionality and embracing Gender+ can be seen in the fact that LGBTQI+ perspectives were seldom explicitly addressed.

A further challenge faced by several IOs was engaging both internal and external stakeholders. Some areas were deemed particularly difficult to address, including the *lack of allocation of adequate financial and human resources* (including relevant expertise), *insufficient engagement and participation* (including resistance and maintaining stakeholder involvement), and a general *lack of awareness* (including limited understanding). These aspects significantly influenced the implementation process and were frequently cited as reasons for revising the timeline or adjusting specific grounding actions. A key lesson learned, therefore, is the importance of allocating sufficient *time and resources* and involve stakeholders at various levels early on – from students to leadership and management – in the development and implementation of the GEP. This create a sense of ownership and involving student unions for example in the design and implementation of roadmap activities was, in several IOs, a game changer for the communication among and participation of students.

Innovation across the institutions is expressed through a variety of approaches that advance gender equality in sport and higher education. These include participatory and culturally sensitive mechanisms such as trusted persons, gender equality teams, and faculty-level structures; creative pedagogical methods like short videos, interactive modules, and case-based learning; and expanded data collection and communication strategies, including dedicated website sections, tailored surveys, and initiatives to increase women's leadership participation. Further innovations involve embedding gender clauses in contracts with sports organisations, systematically updating

curricula with real cases on women's rights and violence, and fostering international partnerships through equality networks. Digital and participatory tools also feature prominently, with hackathons, real-time feedback systems, AI-based data analysis, anonymous reporting platforms, interactive online courses, and centralised monitoring systems. Finally, innovation is strengthened by community-building initiatives such as women's networks, information kits to challenge stereotypes, and the adoption of new gender-based violence protocols, ensuring that frameworks are both inclusive and transformative.

A couple of the recommended areas were less addressed in the IOs' roadmaps. These were primarily "work-life balance and organisational culture" and "gender balance in leadership and decision-making." Innovative measures such as flexible working hours for faculty, coaches, and staff with caregiving responsibilities, or maternity and paternity leave policies adapted to the sports context were discussed during trainings and MLWs, and some IOs already integrated similar measures in their grounding actions.

Based on the planning and implementation process, certain aspects have had a particularly significant **impact** within the project. One challenge identified at the start of the SUPPORTER project was the *lack of gender-related data*, as data collection was initially limited. *Addressing gender-based violence*, including sexual harassment, was another early difficulty. Also, the original IO GEPs hardly included any measurable targets and indicators to assess the impact of the implemented activities. These areas have since seen considerable progress: all IOs have worked actively with data collection and implemented measures to combat gender-based violence, thereby creating impact within their organisations. All the 4I-GEPs embed specific indicators and targets linked to each one of the designed activities within their action plan. This work has also involved the establishment of *reporting and monitoring mechanisms*, such as trust person systems, along with efforts to *raise awareness* among staff and students in connection with these systems.

3. Set of guidelines addressing sport institutions (higher education)

These guidelines, based on the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE 2016) *Roadmap to Gender Equality in Research and Higher Education Institutions* provide suggestions on how to effectively integrate the gender dimension and intersectional aspects into both the regulative organisational pillar (i.e., rules, structures) and the cognitive-cultural pillar (e.g., symbols, values, and images of the organisation). The aim is to ensure that gender and intersectionality are not treated as "add-ons," but embedded as integral elements of the organisation's functioning. To achieve this, the guidelines explore how GEPs, as instruments of structural change, can contribute to meaningful and lasting transformation.

The sports ecosystem remains largely male-dominated, shaped by male-centric and highly competitive cultures. Within this context, gender equality is often reduced to issues of gender balance, focusing narrowly on the numerical representation of women and men. Such a limited perspective makes it difficult to address inequalities beyond numbers and even harder to recognise

other intersecting forms of inequality. This tendency has been described as operating in isolation, in “inequality silos” (e.g., age, disability, gender).

Effective integration of gender therefore requires a transformative approach, one that critically examines both formal and informal norms, values, and practices that underpin inequalities in sport. This approach should incorporate gender alongside other dimensions intersecting with it, such as age, ethnicity, and disability/ability, into institutional structures and practices (formal institutions), as well as into rules and policies (the broader policy and political context).

A GEP is a comprehensive policy document that outlines specific steps and actions to achieve concrete goals. The following guidelines are designed to support the development of such a holistic approach to gender equality, while also providing measures to prevent and address gender-based violence.

The six main steps to develop a Gender Equality Plan

Step 1: Getting started

A first step is to identify stakeholders — the people who will make up the core group responsible for developing, implementing, and monitoring the GEP.

To form this core group, it is important to assess within your own organisation and policy context, including **who should be involved from the institution itself**: for example, individuals who can support the process on a day-to-day basis, such as a gender equality/diversity officer, human resources manager, student and staff representatives, or gender experts. Existing assessment tools can be used as a starting point: 1) the [CASPER](#) (Certification-Award Systems to Promote Gender Equality in Research) tool and 2) the [UniSAFE/GenderSAFE](#) online self-assessment tool to establish a useful baseline to assess performance and prioritise next steps, to support data-informed decisions making as a basis for instituting change, and to compare performance across time to determine progress in achieving goals and objectives.

External allies can also be identified to fill expertise gaps (e.g., in gender analysis) or to provide insights based on their own experience with similar processes. Representatives from other sport faculties, sports organisations and national/regional Olympic federations can serve as valuable partners by sharing good practices from their own gender equality initiatives, offering access to wider networks, supporting training and awareness-raising activities, aligning institutional policies with broader sport governance frameworks, and contributing data or expertise to monitor and evaluate the plan’s impact.

While it is necessary to involve and have the continued and explicit support **decision-makers** (e.g., the dean, president), they do not necessarily need to be part of the day-to-day work of the core group. Their limited availability could risk slowing down the process.

Beyond identifying the stakeholders and their roles, it is important to determine the most effective methods for their involvement at each stage of the GEP development. Distinct groups may require differentiated approaches to ensure that participation is both safe and meaningful. Collective formats such as focus group discussions can facilitate the articulation of diverse perspectives that might not emerge within a homogeneous group. At the same time, staff members or students, may refrain from voicing concerns in mixed settings if they fear negative repercussions.

Regardless of their level of engagement, all stakeholders involved in the development and implementation of the GEP should share a common understanding of the key concepts of gender+ equality. Short introductory sessions by the core group to explain why a discussion on gender is important, as well as the use of a common glossary of terms and other reference materials could prevent misunderstandings and ensure coherence across activities. It is also useful to already investigate possible funding opportunities for the gender equality work **that needs to be undertaken**.

Think of the 4Is

- **Intersectionality and inclusivity:** Ensure diversity within your core group by including members with different profiles (e.g., gender, age, origin) as well as individuals with knowledge and expertise in intersectionality. Use involvement methods that make participation safe and meaningful for each group.
- **Innovation:** Focus on both the composition of the working group and its methods of operation, prioritising participatory approaches and co-creation techniques.
- **Impact:** The composition and mandate of the core group should guarantee that the actions developed are implemented effectively and contribute to the progressive institutionalisation of gender equality within the organisation (refer to the work on *impact drivers*).

Step 2: Analysing and assessing the state-of-play in the institution

This stage will help you analyse the current context of your institution and the surrounding sport ecosystem, so you can target actions that are both innovative and impactful for gender equality.

Consider the five fields of action defined by the Horizon Europe programme (see Step 3)

1. Map the legal and policy context

- Identify relevant laws, regulations, and policies at institutional, national, and (if relevant) regional levels.
- Note any gender equality and sport-specific measures that apply to your context.

2. Assess policy effectiveness

- Check whether evaluations or assessments of these measures exist.
- Identify who is responsible for monitoring and analysing policies and results.
- Verify whether existing monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are implemented in practice or if they are ignored, neglected or have become obsolete

3. Review existing data and reports

- Gather reports already produced within your institution or sector.
- List quantitative indicators (e.g., gender balance in leadership, participation rates) and qualitative indicators (e.g., perceptions of inclusion).
- Highlight gaps where no data is available.

4. Consider formal and informal realities

- Examine formal structures (rules, policies, frameworks).
- Take into account the broader historical, cultural, social and political background that influences gender relations in higher education and the sports ecosystem. This includes

recognising traditions, stereotypes and past practices that have shaped gender roles and portrayals.

- Identify informal norms and practices that may influence gender equality in the sports environment (e.g., gendered coaching practices, traditions around single-gender sports, portrayal of female athletes and coaches, selection procedures, networking cultures, decision-making habits).

Think about 4 Is

- Collect and analyse **intersectional data** using qualitative methods such as targeted surveys, focus groups, and interviews.
- Review existing formal rules and policies to identify gender and **intersectional biases** (e.g., discriminatory eligibility criteria in sports, lack of maternity policies, inflexible schedules).
- Uncover informal recruitment and promotion processes or criteria that may create barriers, and ensure fair and **inclusive pathways** for women, older people, ethnic minorities, and people with disabilities.
- Check current systems for collecting data on students and staff, who is in charge of the collection and analysis and communicate/liase with them on purpose and importance on gender + aspects. This will contribute to an **impactful** GEP.

Step 3: Setting up a Gender + Equality Plan

The findings of the initial analysis allow identifying the areas of intervention to be addressed in a GEP.

The European Research Programme Horizon Europe has defined a number of fields of actions: gender-based violence including sexual harassment, work-life balance and organisational culture, gender balance in leadership and decision-making, gender equality in recruitment and career progression, the gender dimension into research and teaching. All these policy fields have been identified as interrelated and part of a holistic and inclusive approach.

However, the development of a GEP needs to consider the organisation's starting point, and the context that organisations stand within. The focus areas set out for an organisation will depend on the available resources, strategic priorities of the organisation and the formulation of long-term goals.

Not all areas can however be tackled at the same time, and some may be more pressing than others.

To move forward, it is important to start from the results of the analysis conducted in Step 2 and involve stakeholders (both internal and external) through co-creation techniques to design the action plan. The design of the action plan requires to:

- Develop clear and measurable objectives based on the assessment of the state of play and the opportunities linked to the priorities of the organisation, the faculty or of the broader academic and sport eco-system. Sport-specific issues should be given particular attention, including underrepresentation of women in coaching and leadership roles, unequal access to funding and facilities, and stereotypes reproduced in curricula.
- Define SMART objectives and measures for your GEP (i.e. Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Time-related).

- Integrate different types of indicators. Output, outcome and impact indicators are complementary and need to be used together in order to capture not only the implementation of foreseen measures, but also their short-, medium-, and long-term effects.
- Define the timeframe of the GEP, as well as a realistic timeline for its implementation. The duration of individual activities should be clearly specified. When setting timelines, it is important to take into account academic schedules, expected periods of high workload or limited availability (e.g. holiday months, exam periods), as well as key sports events and dates. Key sports events/dates should also be taken into account. This not only facilitates effective time management but also allows for timely adjustments to the activities design.
- Do not forget to establish specific monitoring periods to report on the progress achieved.
- Promote the participation of actors of all levels when defining measures and actions of the GEP. A participatory approach will help define meaningful measures to the actors involved and will enhance their willingness to implement the measures in the GEP.
- Identify and utilise existing resources when planning the measures. Building on existing resources has the advantage of promoting the institutionalisation of gender-sensitive and/or gender-specific procedures or activities.
- Agree on clear staff responsibilities for each measure. The Gender + Equality Plan should clearly indicate 'who is responsible for what and when'.
- Foresee potential challenges and define mitigating measures from the outset. Hopefully, not all of them will materialise, but anticipating risks and preparing responses will make the GEP more resilient and build adaptability to address unforeseen obstacles as well. Build alliances. The measures in a Gender + Equality Plan will not deliver or be achieved unless the Plan is supported by stakeholders at all levels. Take time to explain what the GEP implies for all targeted stakeholders. These efforts need to be continued throughout the implementation of the GEP.

Think about 4Is

- Ensure **diversity** among the people involved in the design, and include individuals with gender and diversity expertise to avoid "gender+ evaporation".
- Design an **inclusive** plan that addresses the needs of diverse groups. See how to attract more diverse profiles by changing the organisational culture.
- Remember that **innovation** can be integrated into the design process of the plan — for example, through the people involved, the fields addressed, unconventional partnerships, new challenges, or out-of-the-box solutions.
- Embed practices into the organisation's regular routines, policies, and procedures to ensure that your plan has a lasting and **impactful** effect.

4. Step 4: Implementing a Gender + Equality Plan

Coordination

- The core team (usually the GEP Committee or another relevant body) is not directly responsible for implementing the entire plan, but rather for coordinating it by mobilising the relevant responsible persons.
- Align with existing governance structures (e.g. Ethics Committee, HR team etc) to increase resource efficiency, avoid duplication and strengthen legitimacy

- Actively involve all identified stakeholders and promote a horizontal sense of ownership across the different institutional services and departments. The core team should aim to have an overview of the ongoing activities and act as the focal point for coordination, rather than being responsible for every aspect of the Action Plan.
- To enable Step 5, build feedback loops into every major activity (e.g. short pre-post surveys, reflection sessions, in-class self-assessment forms for students etc) so both the content and the format of the planned actions can be iteratively refined during implementation. Consider the target group and the sport context when designing the feedback tools and increase responses by distributing in class or during (not after) organised events.

Adaptability

- Implementation should be understood as a dynamic process. The core team should oversee the implementation process to identify what is working well and where adaptations may be required. To do so, regular meetings should be organised with the team responsible for the implementation of each activity. This will help to understand why some measures are not being (fully) implemented and make adjustments as needed.
- Anticipate resistance in various forms (e.g. overt reactions, low interest, reluctance to engage on sensitive topics). In sport contexts, this is frequently framed as gender equality measures undermining meritocracy and competitiveness. Structured approaches, using evidence and positive role models, and confidentiality assurances can help reduce resistance.
- When facing resistance, the 'Realise-Reflect-Respond' cycle can help: *Realise* common triggers; *Reflect* on underlying causes; *Respond* with actions that can de-escalate the situation.
- View resistance not only as an obstacle but also as a sign that sensitive issues are gaining attention, a necessary step toward deep institutional change
- Address participation challenges by adjusting activity formats (e.g. using different data collection methods, shorter workshops, creative learning tools or mobilising student unions).
- Integrate GE topics into mandatory courses to sustain engagement and ensure horizontal understanding across all student cohorts. Communication and visibility
- It is important to give visibility to the Gender + Equality Plan and inform your institution about its existence. Use different channels and routes to communicate to students and staff. Highlights its goal, main areas of interventions, timeframe and achievements.
- To keep the engagement, do not forget to keep in touch with stakeholders you engaged in previous phases. Collaborations with the national Olympic Committee, federations and clubs should be continuous.
- The plan and its progress should be communicated not only to the entire institutional community but also to external allies and partners involved at any stage of the process. Use diverse channels, established in Step 3 and tailored to the needs of the different target groups. These channels may rely on traditional media or non-traditional formats, depending on the institutional, cultural and social background of the organisation.
- Think about the organisation of local events with the sport's actors or participating to existing events. Combining awareness-raising with high-visibility sports events enhances reach and normalises discussions on equality.

Involve the leadership

- Plan meetings with senior management and leadership, they have a key role in supporting the implementation of the plan and the sustainability of action implemented. This will help create ownership of the Gender+ Equality Plan, motivate the staff involved, strengthen the potential of the Plan, and maximise the impact of the Plan's actions.
- Leadership backing should not be just symbolically signalled, but also through resource allocation, formal approvals and integration into strategic priorities and policies.

Systematic capacity building as a main pillar of the GEP

- Make sure to include train-the-trainer sessions and capacity building for coaches addressing both technical expertise and gender+ awareness. As they forge future athletes and leaders, their knowledge, attitudes and practices have a multiplier effect across the sports ecosystem.
- Explicitly regarding GBV, capacity building should be regular, relevant to the sports environment in general and specific sports in particular, and tailored to the needs of the prospective participants (students, academic staff, coaches, GE experts).

Think of the 4Is

- Ensure that the purpose and goals of actions to increase **diversity** are communicated in a clear and strategic way to the entire community. Make privilege and unequal power dynamics visible to those who have it and across the institution.
- Ensure diverse representation in committees and leadership and establish confidential reporting routes for intersectional discrimination with clear procedures
- Incorporate intersectional content into curricula, coach education and staff training and revise established practices that pose barriers for underrepresented groups.
- Keep up to date with **innovative** actions in other institutions and the sport eco-system. Piloting participatory workshops, peer-mentoring mechanisms and creative engagement tools will keep implementation engaging for participants. Experiment with mixed-gender training groups, unisex and inclusive sports.
- Translate successful measures into policies, internal regulations and curricula by securing formal approvals and embedding responsibilities in permanent institutional structures to achieve a lasting impact.

Step 5: Monitoring progress and evaluating a Gender + Equality Plan

Following the assessment done during Step 2 (indicators and data available), establish a system for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of the action plan. Such instruments support effective actions and accountability. By tracking progress and assessing outcomes, the (coordinating) core team can identify areas for improvement and make necessary adjustments to ensure the policy framework's continued success. Furthermore, providing evidence of the effectiveness of efforts undertaken will support their legitimisation and sustainability.

Monitoring is crucial to:

- Enable seeing where and how actions are being implemented.
- Help identify and address potential sources of resistance to change.
- Indicate whether a transformative dynamic exists.

Indicators should be implementation-oriented and adapted to the purposes of the action. Monitoring does not mean looking only at figures and data; other underlying, qualitative aspects also need to be considered. It is therefore important to build on the indicator framework defined in Step 3 to monitor both the implementation of activities and their results. The selected indicators should be systematically collected, analysed and reported at regular intervals to support evidence-based decision-making and continuous improvement of the Gender + Equality Plan. In sport faculties/universities, the indicators should be context-specific rather than generic institutional tools. Besides participation, the indicators should also capture whether curricula, coaching practices, athlete behaviour etc reproduce or challenge stereotypes.

Evaluation is key to sustainability and further enhancement because it:

- Provides evidence of actual changes or lack thereof.
- Highlights the positive dynamics and opportunities brought by gender mainstreaming strategies.
- Is an opportunity to enhance the support to gender+ equality policies.
- Paves the way for future, even more resolute actions, and offers a valuable knowledge for their design.

Transforming complex organisations, challenging processes, routines and power relations among staff takes time. Attention must be paid to short-term and mid-term milestones and potential achievements as well.

A thorough, context-sensitive and mixed evaluation approach helps your strategy to make a substantial difference. Evaluation should not only assess whether actions were delivered, but also whether they have been institutionalised into formal procedures, curricula, or governance structures. Successful measures should be tracked for their potential to be embedded permanently, ensuring sustainability beyond the project cycle.

Think about 4Is

- Monitoring and evaluation systems should pay attention to diversity issues including gender identity and sexual orientation in particular in the field of actions relating to gender-based violence.
- Alongside quantitative indicators, include also qualitative methods (e.g. reflective diaries, collecting student/athlete/coach testimonies) to capture shifts in culture and practices.
- The monitoring and evaluation should aim to be participative and allow voices in all their diversity to provide feedback on progress made, bottlenecks and resistance to change which are part of all organisational changes. It is important to have open and transparent discussions and decisions on what counts as progress.
- Evaluation needs to consider an assessment of diversity, innovation and impact towards organisational change.

Step 6. What comes after the Gender Equality Plan?

A Gender+ Equality Plan will conclude at some point in time. However, this is not 'the end' towards promoting gender+ equality. A new cycle should start. Treat the conclusion of one GEP as the foundation for this new cycle: monitoring results, evaluations, and stakeholder feedback should directly inform new priorities and actions. It is likely that the sustainability of some measures and procedures is already ensured, whereas others may still require further action, or new areas of attention may have been identified. This is the point where a decision needs to be made on how to continue the efforts undertaken so far and what any new Gender+ Equality Plan should address. A

way to move forward can be to use the concept of active hope (Macy & Johnstone 2022). *Active hope: how to face the mess we're in with unexpected resilience and creative power*. First revised edition. New World Library.) to prepare for the Step 1 of the new plan. Active hope is about becoming active participants in the process of moving toward our hopes and, where we can, realising them. To do so, you use three steps: you start from where you are, you identify what you hope for, and you take steps to move in the desire situation/direction.

Sustainability also depends on seizing windows of opportunity, which change agents ready to act when public concern and institutional priorities align.

4. Recommendations

SUPPORTER has developed four sets of recommendations (as factsheets) highlighting the role and contributions specific stakeholder groups can play in addressing gender equality. These four recommendations (presented in subsections 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, and 4.3 respectively) are designed by target group and can be used independently of each other. They address sport universities and faculties of sport, teachers in higher education institutions, sport organisations, and coaches.

4.1 Recommendations for universities and faculties of sport

Sport is one of the largest recreational activities for children, young people, adults, and seniors of different ages, as well as part of high-performance athletes', coaches' and managers' professions. The process of commercialisation and marketisation of sport has led to an increased attention directed towards the ways in which sport can and should be run. In this way, individual practices within sport draw meaning from wider discourses on, for instance gender and sexuality in society. Universities and faculties of sport together with sports organisations, simultaneously are constructing gender and being gendered, and this gendering is linked to power. Here universities and faculties of sport are uniquely positioned to lead the way in advancing gender equality and safeguarding the wellbeing of both students and staff through inclusive GEPs. These institutions are not only responsible for the development of athletic skills but also for fostering the culture of inclusion, respect, and fairness within their academic and athletic programs. By embedding gender equality principles into their core operations, universities can ensure that all students and staff, regardless of gender, feel valued and supported.

Incorporating key values such as integrity, fairness, and respect into the university's ethos is essential for promoting an inclusive environment. Integrity requires transparent practices in recruitment, selection, and opportunities for advancement, ensuring equal treatment for all. Fair play, when applied to academic and athletic contexts, promotes equal access to resources, coaching, and recognition, regardless of gender or other characteristics. Respect, particularly in terms of gender equality, fosters an environment where stereotypes are challenged, and all individuals have the opportunity to thrive.

Implementing comprehensive GEPs and robust policy frameworks is crucial for creating institutional cultures that encourage students and staff to come forward with concerns and ensure their safety. GEPs serve as a strategic tool to address gender disparities, offering clear guidelines to promote gender equity in hiring, retention, career progression, and access to facilities. These

plans also ensure that policies explicitly protect against harassment and discrimination, fostering a safer and more supportive environment.

For faculty decision-makers, HR staff, Diversity, Equality, and Inclusion officers, and Gender Equality officers, the value of GEPs is evident in their capacity to establish clear, actionable measures that hold all members of the academic and athletic communities accountable. Such frameworks ensure that universities not only provide a safe and supportive environment but also equip students and staff to thrive and succeed, ultimately contributing to the creation of a more inclusive and equitable sporting culture.

Recommendations for gender+ GEPs

Getting started: foundations for gender equality

- Clarify the intentions and ambitions of the GEP in a sport specific context.
- Define key concepts (sex, gender and intersectionality) in both binary and non-binary sport contexts.
- Conduct a gender+ audit to identify inequalities in sport (themes of a GEP).
- Secure leadership commitment to gender equality, as being part of the values of the University and education to ensure sufficient and sustainable allocation of infrastructure and resources (budget and personnel).
- Engage a broad range of stakeholders in the design and implementing process of the GEP.

Structural recommendations: building a GEP

- Set clear objectives, targets and monitoring systems for gender+.
- Create/support Gender Committees and support mechanisms and persons (i.e. trust persons) for gender-based violence cases.
- Building a gender-inclusive research and educational ecosystem
- Establish dedicated departments and fund research focused on gender+ and sports.
- Promote interdisciplinary collaboration on gender-focused topics.

Training, awareness and capacity building

- Conduct annually compulsory awareness sessions on gender inequalities and gender-based violence, e.g. on supporting mechanisms for reporting parties and sanctions (disciplinary) for perpetrators.
- Train teachers and coaches and support staff in victim-centred approaches and their roles in addressing gender-based violence
- Promote student-led initiative and peer mentorship (support each other). Include safeguarding training and workshops on whistleblower protection.

Organisational culture and work-life balance

- Challenge stereotypes and normative ideals in the sport environment.

- Address explicitly work-life balance in a male-centric sport context with a strong competitive culture.
- Support work-life balance initiatives, including parental and career break mechanisms for all staff (including temporary, PhD).
- Foster pathways for women athletes to transition into coaching and leadership roles.
- Establish permanent roles focused on gender equality and safeguarding.

Leadership, recruitment and career progression

- Promote gender balance in leadership and decision-making positions.
- Implement gender-sensitive and transparent recruitment and evaluation processes including by revising merit claims and selection procedures.
- Support inclusiveness through education and mentorship programmes for leaders (i.e. gender sensitive leadership).
- Support career development through education, and mentorship programs for including female mentorship and networking.

Gender-based violence

- Establish comprehensive policies, with actions within the 7Ps framework (prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, partnership, provision of services and policy).
- Maintain accessible structures and safe reporting channels.
- Conduct regular risk assessments both within the university premises and outside (e.g. competitions, field work, etc) and ensure psychological safety across university and sport activities
- Make sure that the workplace is a safe place to raise and discuss these topics.
- Plan for sustainability through structural timelines and resources allocation.

Overcoming resistances and sustaining change

- Acknowledge and manage resistance proactively.
- Support change agents through peer networking (both nationally and internationally) and training
- Develop and implement a strategic communication plan promoting gender equality initiatives and successes. Highlight women athletes, leaders and researchers to serve as role models.

Monitoring, reporting and collaboration

- Collect and monitor gender equality data, setting clear reporting standards.
- Publish annual reports detailing progress and challenges for gender equality and gender-based violence.
- Foster internal and external partnership and communities of practice.
- Participate in regional and EU-wide initiatives to advance gender equality in sport and academia.

Building alliance for gender equality

- Frame gender equality initiatives strategically to align with institutional and international goals (e.g., ERA).
- Engage human resources department, ethical committees, student union and senior management as allies.

4.2 Recommendations for teachers and lecturers in universities and faculties of sport

Sport universities and faculties play a crucial role in educating students about gender equality and gender-based violence and also in contributing this knowledge to the wider sports ecosystem through the coaches, managers, physical education teachers, and the athletes they train and teach. Additionally, sports universities and faculties can serve as model institutions, inspiring other higher education institutions and the broader sports ecosystem to promote gender equality through the development of inclusive, innovative, intersectional and impactful GEPs.

The processes of commercialisation and marketisation of sport have led to increased attention directed towards the ways in which sport can and should be run. In this way, individual practices within sport draw meaning from wider discourses on, for instance, gender, biological sex and sexuality in society. Teachers and lecturers are not only responsible for the development of athletic and/or academic skills, but also for fostering a culture of inclusion, respect, and fairness within their academic and athletic programs. By embedding gender equality principles into their courses, they can ensure that all students, regardless of gender, feel valued and supported.

Teaching is often conducted within a binary context, as this remains the norm in sports. This binary context is closely linked to dominant forms of masculinity, which can marginalise other expressions of masculinity as well as femininity. As a result, women students and students identifying as LGBTQI+ may be more vulnerable to inequality or gender-based violence.

Teachers play a vital role in ensuring that all university students are protected from gender-based violence, are aware of where to seek support, and how to report incidents. They also play a key role in fostering an institutional culture that promotes inclusivity and student safety. Teachers are encouraged to rely on their institution's GEP and policy framework to guide their efforts.

The overarching recommendation is to identify your institution's GEP and its implications for your teaching practices and the academic programs that you are involved in.

Understanding gender inequalities and gender-based violence

- Ensure a common understanding within the institution of the following concepts:
 - Sex, gender
 - Non-binary and binary
 - Gender equality
 - Intersectionality in a sport context.

- Ensure that as teachers and institutional staff, you know your rights in terms of safety and are familiar with the contents of your institution's GEP.
- Participate in trainings on gender inequalities and teachers' role in addressing them, on gender-based violence, on supporting mechanisms for reporting parties and sanctions (disciplinary) for perpetrators.

Creating an inclusive learning environment

- Incorporating discussions about gender-based violence into educational settings helps create inclusive and safe learning environments. Students from diverse backgrounds can feel validated and supported when sensitive topics like gender-based violence are addressed openly. This can contribute to improved mental health and overall well-being, facilitating effective learning. Teaching with sensitivity: gender-based violence in particular often involves traumatic experiences, which can be triggering for some students who may have personal experiences with violence.
- Provide mentorship for students to support each other (social and psychological support)

Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content

- Assure that a gender dimension is included in curricula and course content. All students should have at least basic knowledge on gender equality in sports, gender-based violence including sexual harassment, and how sports are ingrained and affected by gender norms.
- Promoting gender + research in sport context as well as research with intersectional perspectives and research on gender-based violence.
- Develop research applications on gender + and gender-based violence in sports.
- Incorporate history lessons on women in sports to highlight barriers and progress.
- Encourage students to write essays and thesis on the topic of gender or gender equality.
- Address the issue of gender-based violence in your teaching: raising awareness, challenging power dynamics and make sure that students know where to seek support and how to report incidents.

Become an advocate

- Higher education teachers have an opportunity to take the lead and push for institutional change

Overcoming resistances

- Recognise that resistance is part of all change processes.
- Implement regular progress assessment towards gender equality.
- Organise regular trainings for change agents on resistance.
- Put in place support systems for change agents to avoid isolation and tiredness and gender fatigue.

4.3 Recommendations for sport organisations

Sport is one of the largest recreational activities for children, young people, adults, and seniors of different ages, as well as a part of high-performance athletes', coaches' and managers' professions. The process of commercialisation and marketisation of sport has led to increased attention directed towards the ways in which sport can and should be run. Everyday practices in sport are shaped by broader social issues, such as gender, biological sex or sexuality. Sports organisations, along with universities and faculties of sport, both reflect and influence these dynamics – they are not only shaped by gender norms but also actively contribute to them. This process of “gendering” is closely tied to power structures within sport. Gendered inequalities in the sports ecosystem are deeply rooted in societal norms that prioritise masculinity over femininity. The perception of masculinity, linked to strength, aggression, and dominance, shapes how athletes are trained, promoted, and celebrated. This often marginalises female athletes, undervaluing their achievements and limiting access to resources and opportunities. The understanding of masculinities in sports reinforces gendered expectations and excludes non-binary athletes, further perpetuating a binary view of sex and gender. Female athletes face stereotypes and discrimination, affecting their performance and overall wellbeing, often leading to lower self-esteem, stress, and isolation.

Additionally, the dominance of masculine norms increases the risk of female athletes experiencing gender-based violence, both within and outside the sport. These incidents often go unreported, as power imbalances and gendered expectations discourage women from speaking out. Sports organisations must address these issues by fostering an inclusive culture that challenges binary gender norms and ensures the safety and wellbeing of all athletes, regardless of sex or gender identity.

As key players in the sector, sports organisations (clubs, federation etc) are in a strong position to lead progress by promoting gender equality protects the well-being of athletes, sportspeople of all ages, and other stakeholders such as coaches, referees, etc.” These organisations are not only responsible for the development of athletic skills but also for fostering the culture of inclusion, respect, and fairness within their sport and athletic programs. By embedding gender equality principles into their core operations, they can ensure that all members of the community, regardless of gender, feel valued and supported.

How to foster an inclusive culture?

Setting the tone for an inclusive team culture and safe environment

- Recognise that gender biases, stereotypes and discrimination exist in sports.
- **Establish a club-wide equality statement** and promote it widely, ensuring all members are aware of it. Explain that no form of gender-based violence will be tolerated, even incidents that are minor. State the consequences.
- **Encourage the use of gender-neutral language** in team names, chants, and communication (e.g., say “athletes” or “team” instead of “boys” or “girls” when addressing mixed groups).
- **Forbid sexist jokes or comments** to create a respectful environment.

Raising awareness and training

- Host **workshops and talks** on gender equality in sports for players, coaches, and parents.
- Invite **guest speakers, professional athletes, or gender equality advocates** to inspire club members.
- Run **anti-discrimination training** for coaches and staff to recognise and address gender inequalities, including unconscious bias and girls' tendency to self-elimination.
- Ensure **awareness-raising and regular training sessions for coaches and staff on gender-based violence**, on supporting mechanisms for reporting parties and sanctions (disciplinary) for perpetrators, and their roles in addressing gender-based violence.
- Educate about victim- and trauma centred approaches, manipulation techniques such as denial of gender-based violence and reversal of victim/offender roles.
- **Provide mentorship** for athletes, staff members, etc to support each other (social and psychological support).

Ensure equal coaching and development opportunities for all athletes

- Organise **mixed-gender training sessions or competitions** when appropriate.
- Provide **equal-quality facilities, training times, and coaching staff** for all teams.
- Introduce **mentorship programs** where experienced athletes support younger players, regardless of gender.
- Support women athletes to stay in sport and to later become coaches.
- **Encourage responsibilities within the club** among all athletes, regardless of gender.
- Ensure for **equal pay, prize money, and funding** for both male and female teams and officials (e.g. referees).

Ensure Equal opportunities for club staff and members

- Challenge stereotypes and normative ideals in a sport environment.
- Develop team-building activities that foster mutual respect and break down gender biases.
- Actively recruit and support coaches of all gender to balance representation in leadership.
- Encourage and support career development towards leadership and management positions of all gender.
- Address explicitly work-life balance in a male-centric sport context with a strong competitive culture. Support female coaches and athletes in relation to work-life balance through innovative mechanisms.
- Secure routines for career break (i.e. parental leave).

Engage families and the community

- Create **family-friendly sports days** that encourage parents to support both boys' and girls' teams equally.
- Partner with **local schools** to introduce more girls to different sports.
- Establish a **scholarship or financial aid program** to support young female athletes facing financial barriers.

- Encourage **male allies** (coaches, players, and parents) to advocate for gender equality.
- Advocate for **equal media coverage, sponsorship, and promotional materials** for men's and women's teams.

Engage families and the community

- Identify if your sports federation has an overall commitment on gender equality and how can this be applied to the reality of your sports organisation.
- What do you want to achieve? Clarify the **intentions and ambitions of a policy framework** or GEP.
- Define what is an **ideal situation of gender equality** in the context of your sports organisation > *provide links toward inspiring practices*.
- Dedicate attention to gender representation in participation, leadership, and media presence. You can also collect information on gendered inequalities through interviews or a survey.
- Communicate your willingness to the members of your club to address gender equality through a policy framework and **involve members (parents, coaches, athletes) in the design and implementation process**.

Specifically address gender-based violence

- Develop **clear policies on harassment, discrimination, and gender-based violence**, ensuring all members know how to report issues safely.
- Have a clear and holistic policy framework with a Code of conduct, including definitions, procedures etc (UniSAFE 7P Model). Develop support systems and reporting mechanisms (formal and informal).
- Ensure infrastructure and resources connected to gender-based violence policy are available and effective.
- Make visible both internally and externally the engagement of the sports organisation towards addressing gender-based violence.
- Have regular risk assessment both within the organisation and outside (e.g. competitions).
- Make sure that the sports organisation is a safe place to raise and discuss these topics.
- For further resources on this topic: <https://unisafe-toolkit.eu/>

Overcoming resistances

Resistance is part of all change processes! Change agents frequently experience isolation, tiredness, and gender fatigue.

- *Have regular assessment of progress and challenges for reaching gender equality.*
- *Offer regular training on resistance to change agents.*
- *Provide support systems for change agents.*

4.4 Recommendations for coaches

These guidelines are based on findings from the EU-funded SUPPORTER project and draw on learnings from the project's partners, eight sports higher education institutions. They reflect outcomes of peer exchanges and collaborative work during a workshop that took place on 20 March 2025.

Sport is an arena where a wide range of children and young people engage in activities. As such, it has the potential to promote equality and inclusion by fostering values and norms such as integrity, fair play, and respect – including respect related to gender. A key figure in promoting these values is the sports coach. Therefore, coaches need to be aware of the factors that shape inequalities in sport and how to address them. Moreover, sports coaches play a crucial role in setting the tone within the team and ensuring that athletes are safeguarded.

How to foster an inclusive culture?

Recognise gender biases, stereotypes and discrimination

The sports ecosystem is shaped by a strict binary view on gender, which can lead to challenges related to gender stereotypes, sexism, and heteronormativity. Sport is male-dominated and male-centred, built upon traditional forms of masculinity – affecting people of all genders. This also contributes to risks such as aggressive and violent behaviour, as well as an increased risk of gender-based violence (GBV), particularly among ethnic minorities, LGBTQI+ athletes, disabled athletes, and high-performing athletes.

All coaches, regardless of gender, position and type of activities, should have access to and take part in lifelong learning and training on gender equality and gender-based violence in sport.

Set the tone for an inclusive team culture and safe environment

Coaches are important change agents and therefore can foster a cultural shift, by encouraging an inclusive and respectful team environment that values all athletes equally.

- **Change starts with self-reflection: challenge your own stereotypes and normative ideals.** This could translate for example into encouraging all players to develop a variety of skills (e.g., don't assume boys should be more aggressive or that girls should play defensively).
- Recognise that communication is both verbal and non-verbal and be mindful of gestures and body language that may unintentionally undermine gender equality.
- **Use inclusive language** (e.g., say “athletes” or “team” instead of “boys” or “girls” when addressing athletes). **Call out and correct sexist jokes or comments** to create a respectful environment.
- Explain that no form of gender-based violence will be tolerated, even incidents that are minor. State the consequences.
- Work with safeguarding to reassure psychological and social well-being of all athletes.

Coaching practices

Coaches can have a direct effect on athletes learning and may influence their health and well-being, therefore there is a need to pay attention to the coaching practice.

- Provide **equal time, feedback, and coaching quality** for all players, regardless of gender.
- Support female athletes by **encouraging them to aim for higher-level competitions**, just as you would for male athletes, aware of girls' tendency towards self-elimination.
- Make sure to respect every athlete's identity and support athletes that do not identify with a binary division of gender to find solutions to challenges such as sex divided dressing rooms, single sex teams and excluding rules.
- Push for **equal access to facilities, equipment, and game schedules** for all teams.
- Integrate innovative, gender-sensitive ideas into their sport sessions, such as mixed-sport sessions and engagement with unisex sports.
- Introduce gender equality into dialogue before, during and after practice. For example, teach boys to leave space and girls to assert themselves. **Encourage leadership** among all athletes, regardless of gender, by giving equal opportunities to be captains or mentors.
- If possible, **mentor or support aspiring female coaches** to increase representation.

Raise awareness

Coaches can raise awareness on gender equality during sport training and practice.

- **Highlight female or non-binary /LGBTQI+ role models in sports** to challenge biases.
- Speak to parents about **encouraging girls to stay in sports** and challenging gendered expectations.
- Collaborate with other coaches to **promote equal standards** across teams of all genders.

Networking

Coaches need supports from peers to be change agents

- Coaches of all genders should participate in an independent community where they can openly exchange experiences and good practices around gender equality. Recreational coaches, who are often excluded from such discussions should be actively included.
- Act as a bridge between academia and practice by holding regular meetings with academics to share concerns and ideas for creating a more gender-equal sport environment.

Advocate for your club and sports federation to develop an inclusive culture

An inclusive culture is important to keep athletes involved in sport and to foster a safe environment for all.

- Identify if your sports federation has a GEP or policy and explore if this can be used to argue for the advancement of gender equality in your club.
- Encourage the leaders in your club to establish a **gender equality statement, as well as a policy framework** and ensure all members understand and commit to it, including athletes, parents, coaches, and organisation leaders. This should include how the club prevents and addresses incidents of gender-based violence.
- Make sure that the sport club is as a safe place to raise and discuss topics on gender+ equality and GBV. Besides established procedures for gender-based violence, support clear guidelines for coaches for handling less severe cases – but still impactful- and fostering a more inclusive and respectful environment.

- Measures to ensure the well-being of coaches to be in place: maternity support, flexible schedule, a coach “sabbatical” and access to a sport psychologist (trained in gender equality and gender-based violence) in each team.

5 Conclusion

The SUPPORTER project demonstrates that developing and implementing 4I-GEPs is both feasible and impactful in sports education and organisations. Success depends on embedding gender equality infrastructures, practices, and cultures, supported by sustained leadership commitment and stakeholder engagement.

By following the six steps outlined in these guidelines and adopting the recommendations tailored to specific groups, institutions can contribute not only to their own transformation but also to broader cultural and societal change in the sports ecosystem. Long-term sustainability depends on continued commitment, adequate resources, and readiness to confront resistance with resilience and innovation.

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